

FEMO: EMOTIONAL DESIGN FOR KIDULTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the problem of kidults immersed in the media. An emerging global market, their needs, their appearance in Colombia, and how through emotional design, the theory of emotions, and Kansei engineering, the result is the design of a product that embodies all emotions and seeks to keep them away from immersion in the media, and to set goals and projects through their hobbies.

KEYWORDS: *emotional design, kidults, Kansei, emotions, hobbies*

INTRODUCTION

Some people always miss the days when they were teenagers, when they did not have big concerns, and maintain the lifestyle of those days, no matter how much time has passed since then. Not only do they keep objects from those days, their attitudes are the same and so are the decisions they make.

These kidults, whose behavior is not in accord with their age, are a new worldwide growing target which experts believe is an opportunity. Their capacity to keep interested in a beautiful appearance and in the fun of every detail is what makes them such a striking target. It is a completely emotional target.

Life is full of emotional moments, which are very intense. In those moments, people are influenced by their feelings about an object. The recreational, the beautiful and the emotional aspects must be included in every person's daily life. All these aspects are inherent in the lives of kidults. These conditions give rise to this project, that proposes to create an emotional object which has an influence on kidults from the very beginning and helps them to enjoy life through new experiences and goals.

BACKGROUND AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Kidults

They are both male and female, but mostly male, aged 25 to 39 approximately, who do not wish to leave the comfort of their parental home. They fear what they might face without that atmosphere. They are narcissistic and individualistic;

they do not want emotional commitments. They continue meeting their friends to play video games and keep mementos of classic characters, such as those of Star Wars. They are consumers of products for children and teenagers, such as Lego and Cartoon Network or Nickelodeon channels. They still use teenagers' vocabulary (Lancheros, 2011).

This recent global trend is called "adultescentes" in Spanish-speaking countries, "nestlings" in Germany, "parasitic singles" in Taiwan, and "kidults" in the United States (kids + adults).

Moreover, Nielsen Company¹ discovered this group of people in a study of television audiences in 2003. The results showed that people between the ages of 18 and 39 watched Cartoon Network more than those who watched CNN.

Since 1970, the percentage of young people around the age of 26 who live with their parents has increased 11% to 20% in the United States. (Hume). "The longest occupied nests in the world are in Latin America, with an average household output of 28 to 30 years", says Maritza Sandoval². (Lancheros, 2011)

Studies have shown scientific reasons for these situation. The Institute of Cognitive Neuroscience at University College, London, found that the brain continues its maturation process for 30 or 40 years (Blakemore, 2011).

Socioeconomic circumstances also have an influence. In today's world, people need to be better prepared for a job, which means they have to invest more time in their studies

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- 1 Nielsen Company is a world leader in market research and information.
 - 2 Director of the Master's Program in Consumer Psychology at Fundación Konrad Lorenz, Bogota.

and therefore go on living at their parent's home. Some kidults who live with their parents work, but make no contribution at home. There are also some who already live apart, but still depend on their parents economically.

In Colombia and Latin America, kidults belong to the higher socioeconomic strata and live in the midst of comfort.

There are no exact figures on how many kidults are in Colombia, but there are projections: according to DANE, in 2005 there were 9'357.000 people aged 25 to 39 in Colombia, and by 2020 there will be 11'594.030.

According to a survey done for this project in Bogotá, kidults of strata 4 and 5 feel their job is monotonous and demanding and get bored at home, although they remain there; they spend much time in the media world, especially socializing in Internet, and their goals and objectives are displaced because of that. They have a saving capacity, like collectible objects and invest in products related with hobbies, image and technology. Their main hobbies are music, photography and audiovisual aids.

Given the above, this project considers as key words: Monotony, obligation, boredom, dependence on the media world.

Definition of Emotions

Figure 1. Theory of Emotions According to Plutchik. It shows the eight basic or primary emotions with their opposite emotion, intensities and the emotions that arise from mixing them.

According to Galimberti (2002), emotions are mood disturbances or intense and brief affective reactions, which are determined by an environmental stimulus and accompanied by somatic conditions.

To understand emotions, Plutchik (1983) raises the above theory (Figure 1). He talks about eight basic emotions: joy,

anticipation, anger, disgust, sadness, surprise, fear and trust. Each one with its opposite and at different intensities, for example, the opposite of surprise is anticipation, surprise with more intensity is amazement, and with less intensity is distraction. From mixing them, other emotions arise. He calls them dyads, which are two primary emotions and their resulting emotion, for example, joy + surprise = delight, and trust + surprise = curiosity.

With respect to the general behavior of emotions, Plutchik (1983) suggests a process, in which the emotion arises from a stimulus, undergoes a process of cognition, reaches the emotional state and generates a behavior and a desired effect.

Emotional Scheme

Emotional design stimulates emotions and seeks to reach people, what they are, what they feel, because objects not only have practical but also symbolic functions. They evoke memories and feelings, and people identify with them. Emotional design brings people closer to their objects. People obtain pleasure from their use maintain an emotional state of enjoyment during the day.

Emotional design helps users feel more imaginative. "Emotions change the way the human mind solves problems" (Norman, 2003). When people are happy and relaxed, they are more creative and imaginative, their cognitive processes are broader; they perceive the general and not just the details.

Three emotion levels are involved in the design of an object: visceral, behavioral and reflective (Norman, 2003). Visceral design is the initial impact of a product, its appearance, touch, and the feelings it produces. Behavioral level is the use, the experience (function, performance and usability) (Norman, 2003). The reflective level implies consciousness, interpretation, understanding and reasoning. "Reflexive design is about relations that can stand for a long period of time, about the sensations of satisfaction which are produced when we own a product and can show and use it, and at this level the interaction between the product and our identity is important." (Norman, 2003)

Product design of this project will give more strength to the visceral and reflective levels, bear on appearance, identity and display; it exhibits and reflects an image by holding the object, aspects of kidults personality.

Kansei Engineering

Kansei engineering was created by Mitsuo Nagamachi to capture the feelings and emotions of humans in the development and design of a product. "It's a technology that joins Kansei (feelings and emotions) with the discipline of engineering. It is a field in which the development of products that bring happiness and satisfaction to humans is technologically presented through the analysis of human emotions and their incorporation in the product design" (Nagamachi, Mohd, 2011).

With this engineering, users give descriptive tags that identify desired product attributes, which are associated with words, images, shapes, colors, etc. that will be part of a product.

Figure 2. Analysis of the issue

THE ISSUE

Through target research, it is concluded that excessive use of the media world is the cause of kidults' feelings of monotony, obligation and boredom. So according to Max Neef (1998) kidults miss amusement, fun, pleasure and freedom.

According to the Theory of emotions and Kansei engineering, this project pretends to stimulate the emotions of trust, joy and surprise, through a new product that keeps kidults away from the media world and allows them to live new experiences, through goal setting.

So this leads the project to two key points:

1. To potentiate needs of leisure, identity and freedom
2. To stimulate the emotions of trust, joy and surprise

To satisfy the need for leisure, the product is expected to encourage kidults to be curious and imaginative; to get involved with the game; to allow them to dream, to relax, to play and to have fun; to go to meeting places in their leisure time.

To satisfy the need for identity, the product is expected to encourage kidults to feel part of a group, to feel coherence, to have self-esteem, to be integrated, to be in spaces where they feel part of a group, and to feel that their symbols are reflected.

To satisfy the need for freedom, the product is expected to encourage kidults to be independent, passionate, rebellious and tolerant and to risk.

With respect to the above-mentioned emotions, the product will stimulate trust in the kidults, making the product a reliable

means to guide them to achieve goals through their own hobbies. The product will stimulate joy and surprise from unexpected experiences in order for kidults to experience pleasure.

This project aims to provide kidults with a new opportunity for fun and amusement, proposing a more human and real contact with others through hobbies and interests other than the media world. It aims to make kidults happier and more creative, because "when people are having fun, they concentrate on the general and not on the details, so they find solutions more easily" (Norman, 2005).

General Objectives

To generate a new option for fun and entertainment for kidults, encouraging them to spend more time doing activities outside the media world and helping them to accomplish goals related to their hobbies.

Specific Objectives

- To stimulate the emotions of trust, joy and surprise in kidults
- To identify form aspects, which stimulate emotions of trust, joy and surprise in this group
- To determine the aesthetic and symbolic look of the product for this type of target market
- To suggest activities that are not dependent on the media world
- To offer dynamic and changing activities
- To encourage kidults to accomplish their goals through their hobbies

THE SOLUTION

Femo complies with the relevant aspects: funny, feasible to produce, dynamic, emotional (dependable, joyful, surprising), transformable, socializing and self-centered.

Femo is a game that guides the user to live experiences by accomplishing goals through his three favorite hobbies such as audiovisual, photo and music activities.

This proposal consists of three collections, each one with a theme of three hobbies. Each collection consists of three Femos. Each Femo has ten figure-shaped holes in his head, one of situations, one of objects and one of amounts. The holes are projected as shadows through internal illumination on a vertical flat surface chosen by the user. Each Femo has a game card explaining the meaning of each figure-shaped hole. Each player turns the heads of the three Femos and each Femo randomly projects a figure. This means three different figures (situation, object and amount) are projected,

Figure 3. Femo three collections.

which set one of the 1000 different experiences that a kidult can live, while accomplishing his goals. The kidult, then, takes the respective game card (see figure 4) and reads what he should do.

When each goal is completed, the user progresses through the game board and the winner is the one that accomplishes the goals set by the game.

There are two options for buying the Femo. The first one: the kidult can buy a Femo, which comes with a card and a game board. This way he will have to share with two other kidults who also have a Femo in order to complete the collection of three and be able to play (see figure 5). The second option: the kidult can buy the complete collection of a theme and invite others to play (see figure 6).

The product is made of plastic (matt PVC) for two reasons: one is emotional --plastic is the material classified as fun (Bramstom, 2010), it provides a soft and warm texture that the user likes, and it stimulates the expected emotions (trust, pleasure or delight)-- and the other technical.

TESTING

It consisted of a questionnaire answered by ten kidults, while they were touching different possible materials for Femo and watching a digital product model. It was carried out to determine whether the perceptual attributes of the product and its function stimulate the emotions of trust and pleasure or delight (joy + surprise).

Conclusions:

- The color of the whole collection generates trust and kidults like it.
- With respect to the texture of the material, the shiny vinyl generates more trust and the matte vinyl, more pleasure.
- With respect to the weight of the material, the matte vinyl generates more trust and pleasure.

Figure 4. Situation game cards.

Figure 5. 1 Femo +1 game card + 1 game board.

Figure 6. Femo complete music collection (three Femos, three game cards, one game board)

- The size of the product generates identity and pleasure, although kidults consider it a bit big to carry.
- The shape of the product generates trust, joy and fun.
- The function of the product generates trust, joy, fun and surprise.
- Kidults like the variety of possible activities they can do; they generate surprise and expectation when turning the Femo.
- They sometimes prefer socializing through Femo than Internet.
- Although kidults like all the activities planned for the game, they prefer those performed indoors.
- The user is not always required to perform with others the activities proposed by the game.
- Although the project is directed to a growing target, it may be a reduced one.

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EVALUATION OF THE CONCEPT

Strengths

- It is based on a new emerging target, which is an advantage because there are fewer products directed to this target.
- The project encourages kidults to live new and different experiences related to their hobbies.
- It generates real human contact, making kidults more sociable and less introvert.
- It lets kidults socialize and belong to a social group through their own hobbies.
- It makes kidults more creative and active and capable of resolving challenges through the game.

Weaknesses

- Because of time limits, the testing was only done with material samples and digital images of the product, therefore, the operating mechanism of the product was untested.